

Role of Relationship Marketing Strategy

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Abstract

Marketing-Mix, correctly the 4P's, has long been recognized as the most crucial marketing arrangement for a business organization. This study has the objective of investigating whether the price component of the 4P's is the most important strategic factor in determining the success or failure of firms in emerging markets like India. Marketing has broad applications, regardless of the type of job or a variety of difficulties. In this article, we discuss five simple marketing approaches that can improve the bottom line performance of your turf or lawn care business. Competitive Marketing Strategy (CMS) has relationship marketing (RM) as one of the key functionality in enhancing business performance.

Keywords: Relational exchanges, emotional wellbeing, trust, profitability, partnering.

Introduction

Marketing can make a difference! Whether marketing sod, irrigation or drainage supplies, horticultural chemicals, and fertilizers, or lawn care support services, the difference between profitability and failure could be the presence or absence of a well-defined marketing plan. The failure or success of companies competing in a market is mainly dependent on the strategy they evolve and perform. The literature is full of references regarding relations between companies having plan and winning and companies that do not have a strategy and fail. One of the primary reasons attributed to failure of companies in the absence of a well-formulated plan (B. Nwielaghi Michael, E. Ogwo; 2013), (WaelMohd, SubhiIdris, Raed A. Momani; 2013), (Sherine Farouk Abdel Al, John D. McLellan; 2013), (RapheephanPhong-wrong, Karun Pratoom, PhapruekUssahawanitchakit; 2012), (Mika Gabrielsson, Peter Gabrielsson, TomiSeppälä; 2012). So, a strategy is an action which leads to the fulfillment of the company's short term as well as long term objectives. Competitive compensation is realized based on three factors (Sudarshan D, 1995):

1. the firm's marketing strategy,
2. Implementation of this strategy and
3. The industry context (Porter's model).

An essential component of the firm’s marketing strategy is relationships. Relationships with channel members, customers, and contestants. He defines each connection by the identity of the partner public and the contract with it.

The objective of the Study

There are two major streams of conceptual and empirical work in strategic marketing that has developed more or less independently during the past ten years (Steinman, Deshpande and Farley, 2000), although the two are inherently interrelated. The Following objectives are designed for studying the role of relationship marketing in competitive

Marketing strategy

1. To Competitive marketing strategies (CMS) is a systematic action setting process as much as it is a dynamic adjustment process. By studying the role of relationship marketing (RM), Proper accordance can be related to RM in the systematic action setting. That helps improve the effectiveness of CMS formulation.
2. By studying the role of RM, marketing programs can be suitably designed to attract, develop customer segments. Resource allocations can be made more effective.
3. If a particular market needs more relational shopping, then that market can be appropriately addressed for strategic decision making by studying the role of RM.

The study is useful for selling strategists who need to take relationship-marketing efforts into account and is also helpful to relationship marketers who need to relate to strategic marketing heads.

Literature Over View

It has been viewed in some earlier studies in developing countries like Nigeria (Sam, Okoroafo; Lloyd C, Russow; 1993)², that the prices of products were often set based on Government’s edicts, and outcomes were made and sold irrespective of mismatches with consumer needs. Perceived Value Pricing is an essential price-setting system in important marketing (Nagasimha Balakrishna Kanagal)⁹. It indicates the importance of providing goods and functionalities to customers and the contemporary need to price it completely so that the firm can take appropriate value. This type of pricing is useful in case of premium and luxury goods, which has a considerable intangible component. It is a fact that some firms capture in their attempts to achieve marketing goals in emerging economies, whereas others fail. To explain the reasons for this phenomenon, a qualitative study (Kumar, V.; Amalesh, Sharma; Rajan, Bharath; Shah, and Riddhi; 2013)²⁴ held transferred, where 42 managers of multinational companies from the United States, Canada, Europe, Asia, and Australia were studied. They observed that consumers in emerging markets are known to be price-sensitive (Sinha, 2005). Price indirectly influences customer loyalty through its positive relationship with product quality (Matta, Devaraj, and Conlon 2001). The choice of pricing strategy—market-skimming pricing or market penetration pricing—will depend on the business objective and the country/market environment.

Nature of Relationship Marketing

At the core of the relationship, marketing is an exchange that is profitable to parties involved in the trade. The concept of trades as it applies to relationship marketing can be observed from both a business cost analysis approach or a social exchange theory approach. The degree to which durable transaction-specific investments are acquired determines the rapidity of commitment given and received, the period of responsibility and the strength of the relation between two parties.

Transaction specific properties (asset specificity in physical capital and human capital) lead to relational exchanges where trust is a prime moderator. As such non-specific exchanges lead to transaction marketing and for trades that are not non-specific, the concept of Association marketing will hold (Williamson, 1979). The Williamsonian approach to understanding relational contracting has been increased (Weitz and Anderson, 1992), by proposing that whenever private possession are made by the exchanging parties in one another, then there is a stronger commitment to the relationship. Many global packaged goods producers regard resellers (wholesalers, retailers) as their customers. The literature cites the case of Gamble and Proctor who see retailers as their Intel and consumers, which has built its company around OEM customers (Webster Jr., 2000). Consequently acquiring relationships with resellers is also an essential part of RM effort in the marketing strategy process. The relationship between manufacturer, reseller, and consumer, as shown below, is a three-way relationship.

Five Simple Procedures

Purchasing Helps You To Understand Your Present Customers Better And To Uncover Innovative Ways For Reaching New Customers. The Customer, Remember Base Is The Hub Of Your Business Because Without Customers There Would Be No Business. Exceeding Consumer Expectations Is The Catalyst That Creates A Lasting Bond Between Your Business And The People You Serve. Consumer Loyalty Has Many Benefits. Philip Kotler (1988), Author of Marketing Management, Reminds Us That Loyal Consumers Are Happy Customers And That Satisfied Customers:

- (1) Are Your Least Valuable Shoppers
- (2) Buy Again And Again;
- (3) Talk Favorably About Your Business, Which Means Free Advertising;
- (4) Pay Less Attention To Competitors; And
- (5) Tend To Buy New Products Or Equipment Lines You May Add Later.

The Following Discussion Briefly Outlines Five Marketing Management Strategies You Can Employ To Satisfy Customers While Simultaneously Improving Business Performance.

Framework of Competitive Marketing Strategy

We first outline a format of the marketing plan and then delineate the position of Relationships in the framework of a competitive marketing strategy.

Format of Competitive Purchasing Strategy

Any marketing approach has to have a marketing intention. Based on the marketing objective, flows two types of analysis – strategic market analysis and internal analysis. Strategic market analysis involves customer management and analysis, market management and analysis, environmental scanning, and future building or scenario planning. Management of relationships with customers and critical external bodies in the market, such as dealers, suppliers, and the government is an integral part of marketing strategy formulation and management. The internal analysis includes strengths, weaknesses, core competencies, resource constraint analysis. The marketing strategy developed is so implemented, and any deviations from the plan are feedback to the marketing objectives and the development of marketing strategies. Pictorially this format of marketing strategy is as below:

Relationship Marketing in Practice

A right product or service should back a good connection. A relationship is a mutual give and take. A relation occurs when the transaction occurs. However, business focus is mechanical, and with human relations, the administrators cannot be automatic. It is advantageous for both people, in good and bad times. One hotel defines the elements of a good relationship to be transparency, honesty, be straightforward, and not discriminate between Indian and foreign customers. Expenses are not the focus in RM; facility development and provision is necessary to RM; the focus is that the ‘Customer should not suffer.’ The hotels act as solution providers. One hotel, for example, provided wireless Internet connectivity, corporate loyalty applications, and general AVIS tie-ups. RM is powerful in hotels; it exists from Secretaries to CEOs. RM efforts are directed at CEOs, decision-making people in organizations, government, ancillaries, related businesses, dealers, individual travelers, travel agents, upmarket socialites. RM efforts are also targeted at leaders who are in charge of bookings. Even a standard smile builds a relationship. Relation development takes place both through personal relation-building and word-of-mouth relationships.

Relationships With The Government Are Also Important. In One Hotel, There Were 70 Licenses Allotted To Run The Hotel. Relationships With The Government Lead To Important Information, Which Can Lead To Help. One Example Is Of A Hotel That Got Advance Information Through A Relationship Of The Location of An International Airport And Bought Land At a Low Price. Apart From Relations With Government, External Partnerships With Vendors, Food Sampling And

Testing Through Microbiology Sections, Employee Satisfaction, Senior Citizen Package Etc. Help Improve company image in the market. association marketing efforts give feedback for strategic decisions such as

1. Opening up of the new hotel,
2. Start of a new advertising campaign,
3. Competition action / reactions to be made.

RM usually is expected to improve profitability, though it is the long-term profitability and not the short-term profitability that is expected to recover. The increase in profitability also comes from the elements of trust. RM managers gather market intelligence and give market information advantages to important marketers, which enable better settlements of the firm to the market over time. RM managers work on experience that is the primary thrust. RMS helps the seller to guide the moments of truth in his favor. The innovative thought in relationship marketing. Is to give what the consumer wants and not what the selling firm wants

Empirical Evidence

To investigate the importance of pricing among components of marketing-mix in marketing strategy formulation and implementation in India, a widespread of companies in a variety of industries were considered. The objective was to ascertain the existence of a relationship between sales (volume as well as value) and sales realization per unit, which is seen as a proxy for price. The year-on-year growth figures were determined for all three dimensions, and for all companies considered. The objective also was to find out the relative movement of volume (and value) with prices, in the industry. For example, the market leader may cut down the costs of its products and gains tremendously in volume/value, at the expense of its competitors who are unable to respond to this kind of price challenges. Sometimes, a price cut could have been implemented across the board by almost companies in the industry with the result that the entire industry grows at a faster pace. It is our considered assumption that many products have tremendous pent-up demand in India and hence proper reasonable pricing, which will enable a large portion of the population to become consumers, goes a long way in expanding the overall market for the product. In other words, the belief is that there is a place for everybody in this kind of market. In this industry, the well-entrenched and established players have been able to grow through a strategy of the combined effect of a slow increase in prices coupled with a moderate increase in sales volume. The resultant force, however, is a substantial increase in sales value. For example, Colgate-Palmolive has increased its prices by only thirty-five percent in fifteen years – from 1995 to 2010. In the corresponding period, volumes have only doubled, while sales value has almost quadrupled. Godrej consumer products have increased sales value by nearly five times, from 2002 to 2013, while it could raise prices by only fifty-five percent. In the period 1999 to 2012, Reckitt & Benckiser has increased its sales volume of household products by more than five times, and its sales value by over six times. In this same period sales realization per unit has gone up by only eighteen percent. This point to the fact that prices are significant in determining sales, and that consumers in India are more focused on value-for-money products. However, their overall volumes are not famous in comparison to the total market. The R-square values for all firms were found to be quite high, signifying a strong correlation between price and volume/value. It was also learned that individual firms had a drop in sales whenever they have attempted a steep increase in the price of their products. So, the results display the same outcomes as having been noticed in the previously discussed industries.

Marketing Strategy Dimensions

The three key-dimensions of an MNC’s comprehensive marketing plan, as previously Mentioned are:

1. Standardization-adaptation,
2. Configuration-coordination, and
3. Strategic integration (Cavusgil and Zou, 2002).

Standardization/Adaptation refers to the use of basically the same (standardization) or different (adaptation) product or service, advertising, distribution channels, and other elements of the marketing mix across countries (e.g., Kotler, 2000; Levitt, 1983; Varadarajan and Bharadwaj, 1993; Cavusgil and Zou, 2002). MNCs following a standardization approach believe that world markets are being homogenized by advances in communication and transportation technology (Jain, 1989; Levitt, 1983). Increasingly, customers in a distant part of the world tend to exhibit similar decisions and demand the same products and services (Jain, 1989; Ohmae, 1985). Strategic Integration is involved with how an MNC’s contentious battles are designed and executed across country markets (Gimeno, Jayachandran, and Varadarajan, 1999; Zou and Cavusgil, 2002). A key to worldwide marketing strategy success is support in all major world markets to gain competitive leverage and effective integration of the firm’s aggressive campaigns across these markets (Birkinshaw, Morrison, and Hulland, 1995; Yip, 1989, 2003; Cavusgil and Zou, 1996, 2002). MNCs may lead their markets and operations in different countries independently or interdependently.

Conclusion

The study started with the premise that price is one of the significant factors influencing the strategy and performance of organizations. A literature survey was carried out to ascertain whether previous studies in different markets had arrived at similar conclusions. Further empirical research, mostly among Indian companies, was conducted with the help of past data. The results of statistical analysis from the collated data supported the premise that price is one the most critical factors in the marketing – a mix of companies which impacts marketing strategy and hence, performance in the market place. All companies, almost without exception, display high sensitivity towards pricing their products. The contention is not that the other factors, like promotion and product, are not necessary. However, in a monopolistic competitive arena like India, prices have overriding importance in the marketing mix of companies, and hence has a maximum impact on the marketing strategy of firms, irrespective of the industry. In this chapter, we have presented comprehensive purchasing strategies as framed by the response to or management of two imperatives: meeting local needs and obtaining on huge competitive benefits. Within this structure, we have identified four generic universal strategies: the international, multinational, global, and transnational approach. We have also shown that these four strategies could be identified by their different positioning on three key-dimensions that are: standardization-adaptation, arrangement-coordination, and strategic integration. We have also demonstrated that constrained by their cultural heritage and organizational, MNCs from different regions of the world tend to follow a particular generic strategy

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